

Homœopathic cancer considerations

An ecological concept

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Introduction

When approaching cancer as a disease it seemed necessary first to consider the range of treatment types available to the homœopathic therapist. Within the framework of the law of similars available treatment can be conceptualized as being of two types. The first broad group are drugs that produce similar symptoms and can be described as paralleling the disease process, e.g. hemlock, poke root in applicable cases.

The second broad group are drugs that are more closely aimed at stimulating the immune system, e.g. nosodes. These can be described as accentuating resistance to the disease process. Within the limits of the work described in this paper, an attempt has been made to develop drugs which are designed to consider these avenues of treatment and to test the effectiveness within limited laboratory experiments.

Consideration was given to the selection of plants from which to develop drugs. New approaches were considered to try to expand the range of raw materials available for future research work.

To this end 'a-priori' models were developed. The first considered cancer tumour growth in terms of characteristics which draw similarities between the tumour and plant community ecology. While it is realized that cancers develop from aplastic cell division, the growth and effect of such cancers within and on the surrounding community of body cells and organs can be seen

as displaying the characteristics of plant species which display parasitism or which are toxic or pathological towards their community neighbours. (Fig. 1).

Experiment 1

Method

The concepts outlined were used to select species from which tinctures were to be derived for testing. In the first case plants which displayed characteristics which effectively smother, strangle or crush their hosts were considered. A number of such types were utilized, but at this stage only one has been tested. This was a species found in Central America which very effectively kills its host tree, was known to the author, and this was available for testing. It is a strangler fig, *Ficus padifolia*, also known as *matapalito*—tree killer. This grows prolifically on palm trees. The vines wrap themselves around palm trees, growing out of the ground at the very base of the palm in several shoots that then wind themselves around the palm. It is common for this invader to completely cover the trunk of the palm as its own trunks merge to form another, outer trunk. The vine then forms its own branches and leaves and kills its host by both smothering its canopy and crushing the trunk. It is an extremely effective agent in the destruction of the unfortunate host.

A tincture was derived from leaves, stem and root of the plant macerated in alcohol for eight days and then attenuated to the potencies shown in Table 1. Preliminary experimental work was undertaken at the Marie Curie Cancer Research Institute. The experimental work was designed to see if this drug was effective in inhibiting cell division and transformation in a culture in laboratory conditions.

In preliminary attempts to assess the efficacy of the drug on cell proliferation, the human peripheral blood leucocyte culture system was utilized. The Mexican strangler fig was code-named Paula and is referred to in the table by this name.

An arbitrary concentration (0.1 ml. of

CANCER CHARACTERISTICS

(Experiment 1) compression and crushing of organs (Experiment 2)

Figure. 1. Model used in selection of plant types for therapeutic use and for experimental design.

TABLE 1 Results obtained from Paula experiment to test cell inhibition abilities. Each potency was tested three times.

Potency	Code No.	Comments
3x	1	Mitoses present—transformation evident—very few cells
	2	Inhibition of transformation—some cell lysis
	3	Cell lysis—inhibition of transformation
Control	4	Good transformation
4x	5	No mitoses—inhibition of transformation
	6	Cell lysis—inhibition of transformation
	7	Lysis—inhibition of transformation
Control	8	Good transformation
6x	9	Cell lysis—inhibition of transformation
	10	Lysis—inhibition of transformation
	11	Lysis—inhibition of transformation
Control	12	Good transformation

sample) of each potency was used in all experiments, which were carried out for an incubation period of 72 hours. Setting up of cultures, harvesting, etc., are by the standard established in the Marie Curie Laboratories.¹

Results are summarized in Table 1.

Analysis

This culture system has been used quite extensively as a preliminary screening method for inhibition of cell proliferation. Normally, cells are stimulated to transform and divide in culture under the influence of the lectin phytohaemagglutinin. Compounds preventing such transformation and division are either immunosuppressive, cytostatic or cytotoxic.

Using different potencies of Paula, the following observations were made.

—Paula 3x is totally ineffective in this system, since the mitoses and transformation were similar to those obtained in the control.

—Potencies 4x and 6x showed inhibition of cell transformation and mitoses with a fair degree of cell lysis.

It is therefore concluded that potencies 4x and 6x of Paula are effective against cell transformation and division.

Experiment 2

The second model considered the normal distribution curve of the response of a population to a disease. In any population some individuals have very low resistance and contract the disease rapidly and in the case of fatal diseases succumb quickly. The next group, the majority, contract the disease more slowly and succumb at later dates. But there is a group of individuals which because of a much higher resistance do not contract the disease or throw off its effects rapidly and fully. (Fig. 2).

It was plants that exhibited the characteristics of the last of these groups which attracted consideration in this work. It was felt that plants which showed most vigour in resisting the noxious attentions of parasites or of other agencies could provide efficacious drugs for the treatment of cancer growths. It was also felt that if tinctures could be made from individuals within a species group which may have been attacked by a pathological agency and had successfully resisted that attack, it was highly likely that the immune characteristics, which the plant had developed or had possessed inherently, would probably be incorporated within the remedy.

Method

Because the initial work was being conducted in New Zealand it was felt that indigenous species should be examined. New Zealand's indigenous species are generally described as a mixed temperate rainforest. The lowlands species are characterized by a podocarp community with individual species names unfamiliar elsewhere. However in practical terms the 'bush' is dense, damp, and vigorous in its growth. Within this forest complex there is an indigenous example of the myrtle family. This species is *Metrosideros robusta*, known locally as the rata. This plant is abundant in the native forests and is responsible for the deaths of many of the canopy trees of the forest. It is a vine which develops from an epiphyte. As the young plant develops, it sends down roots towards the ground. These roots inosculate, and slowly enclose the stem of the

Figure 2. Generalized model of community resistance to noxious agents or disease.

supporting tree, which at last is crushed by the grip of the rata.²

The only tree which can resist the iron hug is the puriri (*Vitex lucens*) the strongest and toughest of all New Zealand trees. In fact it may sometimes be seen bursting the encircling roots of the epiphyte.³ This prompted interest in the utilization of these resistive characteristics in the immune system.

It was also considered that an individual which had been invaded by the rata, but had resisted, would have enhanced the general nature of the puriri species. Its ability as a species to withstand the noxious attentions of the rata vine is so marked that it was very difficult to find an individual which had been invaded by the rata and had subsequently resisted the attack.

Once such an individual had been located, a quantity of puriri leaves, trunk and root was obtained and then macerated for eight days to make a mother tincture from it. The tincture was then potentized to the 12th, 15th and 30th attenuations, using Korsakov hand succussion. Silica glass vials sterilized by heat were used throughout. Succussion frequencies were ten sharp strokes per attenuation. The serial dilutions were centesimal scale and the rest period between each attenuation was just sufficient to refill the vial to the appropriate amount, upon which succussion was resumed by hand each time.

A pilot experiment to assess the tumour-reducing capacity of potentized *Puriri* was then undertaken under laboratory conditions.

Twenty age and sex matched BALB/C mice were randomly allocated into four groups of five mice. Each mouse was injected intraperitoneally with 5×10^3 syngensis Meth A tumour cells.⁴ The mice were allowed food and water ad libitum. The drinking water of the control group was normal tap water, for the three test groups aqueous *Puriri* at potencies 12, 15 and 30 respectively was added to tap water in the water bottles, which were similarly replenished at two to three day intervals. Because of the small volume of *Puriri* 12 available due to a technical problem, *Puriri* 12 was only replenished on one occasion; for the remaining weeks the *Puriri* 12 group drank normal tap water.

The mice were assessed for tumour growth (subjective) and time of death after tumour challenge.

The tumour dose selected was chosen because in the author's experience it would normally lead

to 100% mortality within one month which is a reasonable time to assess treatment effect.

Results

Six weeks after the start of the experiment the condition of the four groups was as follows:

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|------------------|---|
| Control | Three dead (26-28 days); two normal. |
| <i>Puriri</i> 12 | Three dead (one after 15 days, two between 26-28 days); two normal. |
| <i>Puriri</i> 15 | One dead (26-28 days); two with small tumours, two normal. |
| <i>Puriri</i> 30 | Two with small tumours, three normal. |

Analysis

Within strict statistical terms the experiment was inconclusive because there was no statistically significant difference between the groups. However there are sufficient trends indicated within the results to generate some conclusions and to show the need for future modifications in the experimental design.

There was not the expected mortality in the control group because of the restricted nature of the sample and the time scale the reasons for this could not be adequately clarified. Large group sizes would therefore be required in future to show statistically significant differences.

However, there was a trend in the results which showed that the mortality rate of the *Puriri* 15 and 30 potency groups was lower than the other groups. Of particular interest was the 30 potency group in which there was no mortality and the tumour size was also small. In the experimenters' opinion it would be worth extending the trial using larger numbers of mice and a range of tumour doses as a result of this initial indication of success. With larger group sizes statistical testing requirements could be more easily met.

Conclusions

In this paper there has been an attempt to show a conceptual model which related disease processes involving cancer with various plant characteristics. The purpose of this was to create a framework within which plant species could be selected for experimentation. Although the purpose of the experiments was not primarily to test this 'a-priori' model rigorously, the results show that it was a helpful process and may enable many other plants from many areas of the world to be chosen for this and other disease processes.

The experiments described tested the efficacy of potencies derived from two species of cancer

tumour development. Although the experimental samples were small and consequently the results cannot be seen as definitive, the trends established were encouraging within the tentative nature of the programme.

While the first experiment was more definite in its conclusions it is the second experiment which stimulates speculation of further implications. It gives the possibility of a wide field of study in the potential of using survivor individuals as the basis for homœopathic remedies. A lot of work in orthodox chemistry and plant physiology has been conducted in examining the reasons for this resistance factor and subsequent vigour of the plant after the attack by the pathogen.^{5,6,7} This could also be extended to include vigorous noxious species which having been treated by herbicides recover and continue to grow with vigour.^{6,8} The characteristics of such individuals, potentized, may prove very useful.

Bibliography

1 Bishun NP, Morton WRM, McLaverty B. Macromethod

- for culturing human peripheral blood cultures. *Lancet* 1964; **2**: 315-316.
- 2 Laing RM, Blackwell EW. *Plants of New Zealand*. Whitcombe and Tombs 1964.
- 3 Hamlin B. *Plants of New Zealand and Native Trees*. 1962.
- 4 Matossian-Rogers A, Garrido F, Festenstein H. Emergence of foreign H-2 like cytotoxicity and transplantation targets on Vaccinia and Moloney Virus infected Meth A Tumour Cells. *Scand J Immund* 1977; **6**: 541-546.
- 5 Hawkesworth FG. Dwarf Mistletoes on Ponderosa Pine. *Proc. 9 Bot. Cong.* 1959; **2**: 154.
- 6 Lym R. Preconditioning Field Bindweed with Growth Regulators Prior to Herbicide Treatment. Unpublished PhD Thesis. Plant Science Div. North Dakota State Univ. 1979.
- 7 Smith RB, Wass EF. Infection trials with three dwarf mistletoe species within and beyond their known ranges in British Columbia. *Canadian Journal of Plant Pathology* (1) 1979.
- 8 Zemanek DCJ. Effect of the Herbicides MCPA and Simazine on the Respiration Rate and Content of Glycides and Nitrogen in Bindweed. *Biologia Plantarum (Praha)* 1971; **13** (4).